

D2.5 – Technical Documentation of R2:
Collection Module
WP2
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1 Related Documents

- [1] EN 840 www.beuth.de
- [2] EN 14803 www.beuth.de
- [3] DIN EN 30745 www.beuth.de
- [4] BSI-DSZ-CC-0496-2008 Zertifizierungsreport www.bsi.de
- [5] MOBA Operand MAWIS Software Manual MAWIS Mobil
- [6] <http://www.sogisportal.eu/>

2 Glossary

BSI	“Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik” is a governmental institution for certification of IT products in Germany.
CAN	Controller Area network is the standard for event triggered data communication in mobile machines.
CANopen	CANopen is a CAN based communication protocol for general automation systems.
CC	Common Criteria for Information Technology Security Evaluation are internationally accepted rules for certification of IT products.
Chip nest/ Chip holder	Position to be fitted with a transponder. A standardised plastic adapter may be used to fix the transponder in the bin.
CleANopen	CANopen Application profile for refuse collecting vehicles (EN 16815 and DIN30756).
Collection module	This module will be developed as an extension of MAWIS U2 platform of MOBA and is composed of a set of tools to optimize different aspects of the waste collection system.
FDX	Full Duplex Modulation as a data transfer method for RFID . Meaning the interrogator and transponder are transmitting at the same time.
FLASH	an electronic solid state nonvolatile storage memory. This memory is rapid readable, slower in writing. Flash is available as mass storage component.
FRAM	Ferroelectric Random Access Memory. It is a non-volatile memory with rapid read and write access and ultra-low power consumption. It isn't a mass storage component, just for fast buffer in case of power supply loss.
HDX	Half Duplex Modulation as a data transfer method for RFID . It means the interrogator may send energy first and the transponder answers afterwards.
LF	Low frequency is used for RFID in a range of 125 kHz until 135 kHz.
MIP	Moba Internet Platform is a package of server software used for all communication purposes between back office and mobile machines.
MRAM	Magneto resistive Random Access Memory non-volatile memory.
PAYT	Pay As You Throw is a usage-pricing model in the domestic solid waste disposal.
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification is a technology for transmitter-receiver systems for automatic and contactless identification of objects via radio waves.
SOG-IS	see: https://www.sogis.org/ .A European agreement to accept the certification from the partner counties in Europe.

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Transponder	Data carrier, also called electromagnetic label associated with the object to be identified.
Mawis U2	Web tool provided by MOBA whereby the companies can manage the Collection Service tasks. This application will evolve into Mawis U3 (nomenclature to be defined) at the end of the Waste4Think project.
WCC	Waste Collection Company
FIWARE	The FIWARE platform provides a rather simple yet powerful set of APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) that ease the development of Smart Applications in multiple vertical sectors. It is public, royalty-free and open source. More information on https://www.fiware.org .
Asset management module	This is one of the modules of the Mawis U2 and Mawis U3 intended to manage all the inventory (assets) of one Project (i.e. bins, paper bins, etc)
SOTKON	Sotkon is the company that provides the chamber system for the Cascais Pilot. The chamber system allows/block the opening of the bin lid. It is useful to retrieve data from the usage per citizen/user.
FMS	Fleet Management System interface is a standard interface that allows to retrieve data from the engine in order to evaluate different aspects of the vehicle.
ViViVerse	It is the protocol that MOBA uses to interconnect the devices/sensors with the databases.
GUI	Graphical User Interface is the interface that allows the user to interact with an electronic device by graphical icons and visual indicators.
Sencha	Sencha Touch (https://www.sencha.com/) is a user interface (UI) JavaScript library, or web framework, specifically built for the Mobile Web. It can be used by Web developers to develop user interfaces for mobile web applications.
Web Services	A web service is a service offered by an electronic device to another electronic device, communicating with each other via the World Wide Web.

3 Executive Summary

The present document is intended to expose the developments MOBA is carrying out within the W4T project. Hereafter, one can see the participation of MOBA as a provider of the IT tools that will be used by EMAC (in the pilot of Cascais). The technical contribution for the Collection Module is gathered into the Work Package 2 (WP2).

On the one hand, there are tasks destined to software improvements over the existing MawisU2 web platform and the MIP communications platform. On the other hand, some efforts are dedicated to the hardware developments (i.e. the upcoming on-board computer mini-Operand that will be installed in 4 trucks of the Cascais fleet).

An introductory part will give the reader a general view of the complete MOBA solution for the Cascais Pilot and the software improvements to be met within the W4T. Next, some of the existing hardware tools are presented in order to ease the understanding of the complete system installed in Cascais. Further technical details of the components can be found in the Annexes. The upcoming on-board computer, the mini-Operand, is not described hereupon. It will be shown in D2.6 since it is under development and is scheduled for the end of 2018.

All the data coming from the on-board computers can be seen on a web platform thanks to the communications platform. The communications layer in MOBA is managed by the MOBA Internet Platform ([MIP](#)) which is described after the electronic components.

Finally, the document describes the advancements to be included (or already included) in the existing [Mawis U2](#) Platform based on the Grant Agreement proposal. The upgrades defined herein meet the requirements within the W4T to help the Waste Collection Companies ([WCC](#)) more efficient and environmental-friendly.

Last but not least, the reader will find a testing section that shows real data from the sensors installed in Cascais. So far, data is coming from the vehicles and the Filling Level Sensors. Data from the chambers are not yet available with MOBA.

To sum it up, the reader can find an overview of the complete solution offered by MOBA for a Collection Service reinforced with the presentation of the components required for such a system. Next, the software developments that will complete the [Mawis U2](#) platform are detailed. The main idea is focused on the data collection from the Filling Level Sensors, the trucks and the Chambers. Consequently, it can be used to optimise the service, foster the eco-driving and implement the [PAYT](#) scheme in the municipality. Additionally, MOBA will integrate its platform with [FIWARE](#) to share relevant data of the pilots.

4 Introduction

The main purposes for the bin identification system based on RFID technology are the automatic collection of data for:

- a) Costs-by-cause principle fee accounting system (PAYT) with the aim to increase the motivation of citizens to waste separation in their household. The result will be a decrease of garbage and increase of reusable materials.
- b) Decrease the costs for logistic in solid waste disposal.

This technology has been in operation for many years. Within the Waste4Think project and the WP2 Collection module, different tasks are carried out to improve the system and suitability for new markets:

T2.1 Sensor Platform

- Filling Level Sensors

T2.2 Software Platform

- Improvements over the existing platform Mavis U2
- Inclusion of the Chamber Management module
- Integration between [SOTKON](#) platform and MOBA platform
- Integration between [FIWARE](#) and MOBA platforms

T2.3 Waste Collection Optimization with the subtasks

- T2.3.1 Web based Application Mavis U3 **the Collection module**,
- T2.3.2 MIP Communication on Back-end Software,
- T2.3.3 Mobile device Mini Operand and firmware

Additionally, MOBA will participate in the WP5 as follows:

T5.3.2 Develop software modules to calculate waste tariffs and to generate invoices starting from the parameters decided in the new local regulation of Cascais Portugal.

These tasks are improvements in the existing system for a better acceptance in southern European markets.

This document will give an overview about the whole identification and software system to ensure a better understanding of the **Collection module R2**. Chapter [9](#) and [10](#) explain the collection Module R2 itself. In chapter [5](#), [6](#), [7](#) and [8](#) the description of the products offered by MOBA for such markets is given. In addition, some of them are currently in use in the Cascais Pilot. Finally, on section [11](#) one can see some real data taken from the Cascais sensors.

The [MIP](#) improvements task T2.3.2 is under development and will be described in the document deliverable D2.6 in month 34. The same is valid for the new hardware development T2.3.3 Mini Operand. This device will be an additional board computer in the model series with some unique features.

In order to present the whole architecture in a generic view, the following schema () draws the connections and the relation between the components integrated in the Cascais Pilot. Since MOBA already has the middleware platform ([MIP](#)), all devices send the information directly to the MOBA databases. Then, there will be a horizontal connection between MOBA and the FIWARE platform.

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Figure 1 - General view of the structure for the components in the Pilot of Cascais

Furthermore, in the following Figure 2, one can see how the results from the Collection Management developments (R2) are related to the other results within the W4T.

Figure 2 - Modules architecture

Hereunder the relation between Functional Requirements and the components or developments.

Functional Requirements

R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation	
R1_FR1.1	Allow user identification to the collection system	-
R1_FR1.1.1	Allow user identification via ID card (NFC)	-
R1_FR1.1.2	Allow user identification via an iBag (RFID)	-
R1_FR1.1.3	Allow bin identification via RFID tag (D2D system)	Container equipment
R1_FR1.2	Monitor the delivery of waste (control access)	Chamber system, Integration with Sotkon devices
R1_FR1.2.1	Control access to containers using a black list mechanism	Chamber system, Integration with Sotkon devices
R1_FR1.2.2	Control access to the containers using a white list mechanism	Chamber system, Integration with Sotkon devices
R1_FR1.2.3	Locks must be reprogrammable	-
R1_FR1.3	Allow characterization of the deposited waste	-
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)	-
R1_FR1.3.2	Provide help in the identification of improper waste when emptying the bin/bag	-
R1_FR1.3.3	Get the amount of waste deposited	-
R1_FR1.3.4	Get the time when the waste is generated (deposited or surplus)	-
R1_FR1.3.5	Get the localization where the waste is deposited	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR1.3.6	Get the number of iBags delivered to users	-
R1_FR1.3.7	Monitoring the waste deposited in Eco-events	-
R1_FR1.4	Get information about the state of the deposit point and composting plants	-
R1_FR1.4.1	Allow the monitorization of the filling level (Bins)	-
R1_FR1.4.2	Allow the monitorization of the temperature (Composting)	-
R1_FR1.4.3	Allow the monitorization of moisture (Composting)	-
R1_FR1.5	Be a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker	-
R1_NFR1.1	The system must be auditable	-
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route	
R1_FR2.1	Get the total fuel consumption on a collection route	Vehicle equipment, Eco-driving
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact on a collection route	-
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route	Vehicle equipment, Software platform
R1_FR2.4	Get the FMS information from the CAN BUS	Vehicle equipment, Eco-driving
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected	Vehicle equipment, Software platform
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bins have been collected	Vehicle equipment, Container equipment
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bins have been collected	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR2.8	Allow to emit a certification of the work done during the shift	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues	
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container	Vehicle equipment

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R1_FR3.2	Allow reporting of container vandalization	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.3	Allow reporting of incorrect use of a container or bag	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.3.1	Allow reporting of the presence of improper waste	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.3.2	Allow detection of non-inventoried containers	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow reporting of a missing container	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.4	Allow evidence collection (photos or videos) of incidents	Vehicle equipment
R1_FR3.5	Allow requests for specific collections (bulky waste)	-
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system	
R1_FR4.1	Allow showing the state of the waste collection system	-
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow showing the {past, current, planned} state of the system	-
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns	-
R1_FR4.3	Allow personalisation of the monitoring system	-
R1_FR4.3.1	Allow the filtering of information provided by time, type and geographical distribution	-
R1_FR4.3.2	Allow selection and configuration of the KPIs to show	-
R1_FR4.3.3	Allow definition of alerts	-
R1_FR4.4	Allow creation of automatic reporting in PDF, Excel and CSV	-
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences	-
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook	-
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages	-
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information	
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution	-
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems	-
R1_NFR6.1	The communication channel should be secure (un-authorized person should not be able to read a message)	-
R1_NFR6.2	The communication channel should be reliable (no information can be lost)	-
R1_NFR6.3	Provide bidirectional communication system	-
R1_NFR6.3.1	Provide bidirectional communication system between the {back-end, MAWIS and Wintariff} and the sensors	-
R1_NFR6.3.2	Provide bidirectional communication system between the {back-end, MAWIS and Wintariff} and the truck	-
R1_NFR6.3.3	The communication system should use the FIWARE platform	Software Platform
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server (for MOBA components)	MIP Platform
R1_FR5.3.1	Secured data transmission for PAYT	MIP Platform, Integration with Sotkon devices
R1_FR5.3.2	Data transmission for real time reporting	MIP Platform, Integration with Sotkon devices
R2_FR1	To manage the waste collection service	
R2_FR1.1	Creation of routes to be followed by each vehicle of the fleet	Software Platform, Waste Collection Optimisation
R2_FR1.1.1	Dependent on the filling level of the bins	Sensor Platform, Software Platform, Waste Collection Optimisation
R2_FR1.1.2	Dependent on the incidents declared	Software Platform, Waste Collection Optimisation
R2_FR1.1.3	Dependent on vehicle and driver availability	Software Platform, Waste Collection Optimisation

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R2_FR1.1.4	Dependent on traffic conditions on routes	Software Platform, Waste Collection Optimisation
R2_FR1.2	Optimize the routes of the fleet	-
R2_FR1.2.1	Optimize the routes minimizing the time	-
R2_FR1.2.2	Optimize the routes minimizing the distance	-
R2_FR1.2.3	Optimize the routes minimizing the cost	-
R2_FR1.2.4	Optimize the routes minimizing the environmental impact	-
R2_FR1.2.5	Optimize the routes with any combination of the above	-
R2_FR2	Provide feedback to drivers	
R2_FR2.1	Provide turn-by-turn information to the driver	Vehicle equipment, FollowMe, Waste Collection Optimisation
R2_FR2.2	Provide tips to promote more sustainable driving	Vehicle equipment, Eco-driving
R2_FR3	Calculate the taxes to be charge to the citizens (invoicing module)	
R2_FR3.1	Be able to calculate taxes following different PAYT schemes	-
R2_FR3.1.1	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme including incentives for the use of the different prevention and recycling actions	-
R2_FR3.1.2	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme base on the amount of waste generated	-
R2_NFR3.1	Fulfilment with the calculation method established by the Municipality Regulation	-
R2_NFR3.2	Generation of transparent bills	-

5 System overview

For the automatic identification (and, optionally, weighing) of bins and containers on waste collection vehicles, all containers are fitted with a data carrier (transponder) and electronically assigned to the user in a database. By assigning the data carrier to the user,

- a) each emptying is automatically assigned to the correct user and can be billed precisely, and
- b) containers not approved for emptying (non-assessed, not part of the cycle and stolen) can be excluded from disposal and localized in a targeted manner.

The sequence for data collection of emptying data with an identification and weighing system are shown in Figure 3. Behind the visible components are some necessary additional services for bin assembly, software and maintenance of all main parts.

Figure 3 - Complete collection system

6 Container equipment

All bins or containers must be equipped with a [transponder](#) for the automatic identification during dumping process. There are different technologies available on market.

In the European norm the [LF transponders](#) are foreseen for two wheeled and four wheeled bins.

6.1 Data carriers for the containers – transponders

The specification and mounting location of the [transponders](#) must meet the requirements of [EN 14803](#) [2], [EN 840](#) [1] and [DIN 30745](#) [3].

For mounting in the [chip nest](#) of plastic containers are available as an alternative

- [HDX transponder](#) with antenna coil wound on a ferrite core and
- [FDX](#) or [HDX transponder](#) without core (air-core coil).

[HDX transponder](#) with ferrite core

Advantages: Approximately 30cm reading range, hermetic encapsulation of the electronics and antenna in a glass tube, magnetic field horizontally aligned with the comb bar (as a result, the antenna can be mounted in a protected manner behind the teeth and container recognition is possible at least two teeth).

Disadvantage: During mounting, it must be ensured that the [transponders](#) (Figure 4) are precisely aligned in the [chip nest](#).

Figure 4 - HDX transponder

[FDX](#) or [HDX transponder](#) with air-core coil (Figure 5)

Advantage: No alignment necessary during mounting.

Disadvantages: Short range (antenna must therefore be mounted at one of the teeth on the comb bar, which mechanically endangers the antenna and necessitates the use of special "identification combs"), vertical orientation of the magnetic field (to identify the container, it must always hang with its [chip nest](#) exactly on the tooth with the antenna).

Figure 5 - FDX transponder

Typical [transponders](#) for waste bins and containers are shown in [Annex 1](#).

6.2 Container equipment and assignment

Delivery of new containers: When issuing new containers, the transponders are delivered to the container manufacturer, who mounts these in the bins at the factory. During distribution of the containers, the container label is applied on-site. The bar code printed on the label contains the bin information with bin number, waste type and bin size. After delivery of the bin, both the barcode and transponder number will be read with a handheld scanner to create the data connection for the database.

Equipping already existing containers on-site: When equipping existing containers, the transponders are mounted onto the containers on-site. The bin label is applied to the bin. The bar code printed on the label contains the bin information with bin number, waste type and bin size. After the assembly of the transponder in the bin, both the barcode and transponder number will be read with a handheld scanner to create the data connection for the database.

You can see a sample for a bin label in [chapter 6.4](#).

It seems the information on the label is redundant to the transponder. This isn't the case on the real application. There is a need for visual identification of the bin on the part of the citizen and also the team on the refuse collecting vehicle. The owner of bin as well as the team on the refuse truck have to make sure that the bin is back in the right location.

6.3 Public information about container assignment and PAYT

The introduction of a PAYT needs more publicity informing the public and motivating them to cooperate for their own benefit. Without open communication, the reactions of the public can go in unexpected directions.

6.3.1 Public relation in preparation of PAYT

The municipality should inform the citizen about each step in preparation of a PAYT. The better the motivation in the usage of waste separation, the better the recycling rate will be. That will have a decreasing effect on the fees for waste disposal. There is an array of different channels that can be used to educate the public: Newspapers, Homepages, social media and events will get the support with all available information. There are templates available from other reference projects.

The games from SGI are a good extraordinary opportunity to transfer the PAYT idea and the knowledge of waste separation itself. The members of the W4T consortium assume that these game based learning applications, so called serious games are accelerating the learning curve of citizens in usage of the waste separation.

The serious games products will be a part of the optional software tools in the whole public relation package. The sale of these products is integrated into the marketing strategy of the complete system.

6.3.2 Support in design of accounting system for PAYT

The design of PAYT fee calculation rules are a challenge for the municipalities, when doing this for the first time and only being experienced in flat rate systems. It is recommended to engage a consultant for that task. It should be a consultant with a good knowledge about PAYT and the local conditions. Furthermore, the consultant should be an independent company or institution without commercial interest to promote any kind of product or supplier. Only this prerequisite guarantees the selection of the best matching solution from the market.

More important is for the tendering process. Only an independent consultant can be involved in a tender preparation. The W4T consortium should consider this, or the municipalities will find themselves running into an illegal tender situation. That can lead to a cancellation of the tender by competitors or opponents of the system.

A cooperation of system suppliers and consultant companies is possible and recommended on scientific basis, but it should be independent on commercial basis.

6.3.3 Public relations for bin or container assembly

The citizens should be informed about the forthcoming container assembly on-site by using a circular letter. The letter should include general information regarding the organization of the bin assembly on-site.

The citizen should support the service to keep the bin on street for the duration of assembly. For that reason, the letter should give the exact period for the service in the particular area.

The highest installation rate can be reached by these individual letters and so the maximum number of container assignments.

The letter should also include a temporary paper label with container data based on the available information. The citizens tape the stickers on the top of their bins. This helps the teams find the right bins and the container assignment. Concurrently the citizen has information about the number of bins which will be assigned.

This information is important for citizens to learn more about the intention of changes in the waste disposal. They should know, which advantages can be created by changing the behaviour in personnel waste management.

6.4 Container labels

To visually mark the containers, container labels are necessary.

Technical specifications:

- Material: PVC (weatherproof)
- Printing method: thermal transfer
- Layout: custom
- Size: 110 x 50 mm (standard format)
- Contents: according to specifications, plain text and bar code
- UV resistance: yes
- Removable: not without damage

The PVC material ensures a long-term use of 10 years. A special glue for Ethylene and a structure in the label guarantee that the label is not or only with damages removable from the bin.

A container label is shown as an example in Figure 6. The minimum amount of information is the bin number and the address of location.

Figure 6 - Container Label

6.5 Equipment for printing container labels

There is a label printing system (Figure 7) for printing weatherproof PVC container labels. Labels can be printed directly from the container management software.

Figure 7 - Label Printer

ETISYS EP-726 label printer

Technical specifications:

- Printing method: direct thermal and thermal transfer
- Max. printing width: 104 mm
- Media width min - max: 19 - 118 mm
- Resolution: 203 dpi
- Max. printing speed.: 100 mm per second
- Memory: 8MB SDRAM
- Interfaces: Centronics, RS232, USB
- Dimensions: width: 231 mm, depth: 289 mm, height: 270 mm
- Weight: 4.5 kg

7 Vehicle equipment

The vehicle equipment is responsible for the correct identification of each bin or container during the dumping process. The event of emptying is stored with bin identification number, date, time, GPS position and optionally with net weight and event information.

The vehicle equipment should store the data to save against data losses. There are various methods and mechanism integrated into the mobile software application to ensure the integrity of data for PAYT. The common request for data integrity is the certification of system in accordance with the rules of the CC.

7.1 Overview

The vehicle equipment for bin identification collects the data automatically during the dumping process . Each emptying of a bin or container is stored with the identification number of bin, date, time, GPS position and can be optional more data.

The system can easily be extended by a weighing system. This weighing system doesn't play a role in Waste4think and is not descript in detail in this document.

The following schematic shows the general structure of an identification system for refuse collecting vehicles. The system can work as a simple data collection equipment in the background or with a human machine interface. There are two different board computers available.

Setup of the vehicle equipment (Figure 8)

a) Example with 2 antennas for 2 identification points, lifter lock and C/eANopen interface

Figure 8 – Setup of the vehicle equipment

7.2 Example 2 detection points, without lifter lockout

The schematics shown in Figure 9 are for a truck equipment bin identification for split lifters. The board computer is the fixed mounted device with a display and touch screen for the job and tour management. The system works with sensors assembled at the lifter to get information about the position of the lifter and bin presence.

Figure 9 - Truck equipment for bin identification with Operand

7.3 Example with 2 detection points, lifter lockout, CleAN_{open} interface

This is a similar truck equipment (Figure 10) for identification as was shown in [7.2](#). The difference is the interface to CleAN_{open}. This is the state of the art interface between all components on the refuse collecting vehicles.

The information is available via this CleAN_{open} interface instead of using separate sensors.

Figure 10 - Truck equipment for bin identification with Operand (alternative)

7.4 Example with 2 detection points, lifter lockout, C/eAN_{open}

The truck equipment with CG1 (Figure 11) as board computer recognition system working in the background. The elementary data collection function is the same as it is in [7.2](#) and [7.3](#). The difference is the missing job and route list with the opportunity to show events or navigation information on a map. Furthermore, there are less opportunities for extensions like camera solutions and map related software.

Figure 11 - Truck equipment for bin identification with CG1

7.5 Mounting the vehicle equipment components

This chapter shows, in Figure 12 and Figure 13, the sample assembly on refuse collecting vehicles.

7.5.1 Variant with expanded On-board computer “MOBA Operand” in cabin

The MOBA Operand is assembled in the driver cab (Figure 12, left). This device is the human machine interface for the job management, navigation and data collection tasks.

The identification computer is assembled at the rear of the refuse collecting vehicle (Figure 12, right).

Figure 12 - (left) On-board computer in cabin, (right) Identification computer on lifter

7.5.2 Variant with On-board computer “CG1” on lifter

In this variant all components are mounted on the lifter (Figure 13). This can be useful, if the lifters are often changed between the trucks.

Figure 13 - Board computer at the lifter (left), (right) Identification computer on lifter

7.6 Type and arrangement of antennas

The design and arrangement of the antenna depend on the transponder and the lifters used. The optimum choice of antenna is determined on-site during a vehicle inspection and by means of tests. The typical antenna types are shown in Figure 14.

When using the offered **HDX transponder**, a so-called "rear comb antenna" can be used as the HDX transponders have a very long range due to the use of ferrite cores in the antenna coil and, in addition, the magnetic field is orientated horizontally along the comb bar. With the rear comb antenna, the reading range is so large that the transponder can also still be read "one tooth further". As a result, containers with a narrow comb bar can hang all the way to the right or left, for example, and still be reliably identified.

When using the offered **FDX transponder**, a so-called "tooth antenna" must be used because the FDX transponders, with their air-core coil, have a shorter range and the magnetic field is orientated vertically. To use the tooth antennae, appropriately prepared comb bars (so-called "identification combs") must be provided by the lifter manufacturer.

Figure 14 - (left) Rear comb antenna - typical when using HDX transponders, (right) Tooth antenna - typical when using FDX transponders

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For the identification of metal containers or containers that are picked up via lift pins, an antenna near the lift truck is used (Figure 15)

Figure 15 - (left) Rear comb antenna for the identification of metal containers 1.1m³, (right) Rear comb antenna for the identification of metal containers 3m³ up to 5m³

7.7 Identification computer

The intelligent identification computer Ident Control IDC30 (Figure 16) is located on the lifter and performs the identification and signal processing (timing, processing of sensor signals for the lifter lockout, etc.) as well as activation of the antenna(e). The figure shows an identification computer for connecting up to 2 antennae

Figure 16 - Identification control IDC30

Technical specifications:

- Housing: aluminium die cast
- Size: approx. 220 x 120 x 90 mm
- Weight: approx. 1.7 kg
- Protection rating: IP 66
- Resistance: resistant against aggressive materials
- Operating temperature: -30°C to 70°C
- Power supply: 8...34 VDC, load dump resistant
- Transponder types: HDX: TIRIS*, FDX 125/134 kHz
- RF channels: 2x long range HDX *¹
1x long range HDX or 2x short range HDX/FDX *²
- Interfaces: CANopen or RS232/422/485
- Digital inputs: 7x optionally NPN/PNP
- Power switching outputs: 4x PNP

*¹) Basic variant

*²) Extended variant (additional)

* TIRIS is a registered trademark of Texas Instruments Inc (TI)

7.8 CG1 on-board computer

Due to its compact design and high protection rating, the CG1 on-board computer (Figure 17) is ideally suited for outdoor installation. It is standardly equipped with a GPRS radio data device and a GPS receiver. Optionally, additional emptying data can be captured by connecting identification computers and weighing data can be captured by connecting a calibrated scale. The operating personnel can also manually enter information via additionally connected operating units. All captured data is cyclically transmitted with GPS position to MIP.

Figure 17 - On-board computer CG1

Technical specifications:

- Housing: polyester, grey
- Size (W x D x H): approx. 162 x 82 x 62 mm (without cable glands, without fitting panel)
- Weight: approx. 1.0 kg (incl. fitting panel)
- Protection rating: IP67
- Operating temperature: -25°C to 75°C
- Power supply: 8.. 30 V DC (vehicle power supply), max. 0.3 A
- Terminals for external connections (*1): 2x CAN, 3x RS 232, some with power supply, also for external GPS mouse, 1x of which with hardware handshake
- External connection: CAN service socket
- Data memory: FRAM 8kB, industrial SLC Micro-SD card, socketed or soldered
- Display: B/W, 128x64 pixels, LED backlighting
- Keyboard: 16-key keyboard with RESET function
- Certifications: CE acc. to EMC Directive 89/336/EEC

*1) These interfaces are only available externally if not already used by internal modules.

Display elements on the CG1 on-board computer (Figure 18):

Figure 18 - Display elements on the CG1

7.9 MOBA Operand on-board computer

The MOBA Operand on-board computer (Figure 19) was designed as a typical cockpit computer and therefore has a large colour display that can display, e.g., order lists, digital maps or a high-resolution camera image. Operation is possible via both the large illuminated buttons with pressure points as well as on the touch-sensitive screen (touch screen).

Figure 19 - On-board computer

Technical specifications:

- Manufacturer: MOBA
- Housing: cast aluminum with powder coating
- Size (W x D x H): 205 x 52 x 152 mm
- Weight: approx. 1.5 kg
- Protection rating: IP 51 (optionally up to IP 66)
- Operating temperature: -30°C to 70°C
- Power supply: 8...30 V DC (vehicle power supply), max. 1.5 A
- Computer core: Freescale i.MX 6 Quad Core with 800 MHz, 1GB DDR3-RAM, 8 kB FRAM, 1 GB SLC μ SDHC, Microsoft Windows Embedded Compact 7
- Display: 7" transmissive color TFT, 800 x 480 pixels, format 16:9, up to 600 cd/m², infinitely adjustable brightness, ambient brightness sensor
- Operator interface: membrane keyboard (illuminated) and touch panel, built-in loudspeaker
- Data carrier: robust USB memory stick, SLC 512 MB (up to 16 GB MLC) (>IP 65)
- Interfaces: 2x CAN, RS 232 with power supply, GPS mouse, USB host
- Options: externally exchangeable MicroSDHC card and SIM card for GPRS
- (Internally installable): wireless communication, WLAN, GSM/GPRS, GPS (EDGE/ HSPA/ CDMA on request), each antenna either integrated or external, additional internal MicroSDHC card up to 32 GB, up to 4x RS 232 with power supply, up to 4 PAL cameras can be connected, up to 5x USB hosts (some internally), USB slave, 10/100 MB Ethernet connection, speaker phone for telephony

Deliverable D2.5

The document MAWIS Software Manual MAWIS Mobil [5] contains the user guide for the whole software application. Here are some examples from this chapter (Figure 20, Figure 21 and Figure 22).

Examples for operating steps and screen displays on the on-board computer:

MAWIS waste disposal	
MAWIS- Demotour, Löbtau	▲
300 24/03/10	
STD KM 790 (PPK)	▼
44095 24/03/10 - 25/03/10	
Paper on Thursday	
300 Thursday	
300	
300 prepared: 23/03/10	
Empty tour in count mode	OK
-1	
0	24/03/10 17:52:55

MAWIS waste disposal	
Kronenstr.	20 0/1
Ⓜ Kronenstr.	20 3/2
01129 Dresden, Trachau (Zahnarzt)	
Kronenstr.	22 3/5
Kronenstr.	24 1/2
Kronenstr.	26 1/1
Kronenstr.	27 0/2
Kronenstr.	29 0/1
Wilder-Mann-Str.	37 0/2
21 / 411	0 / 0 24/03/10 14:44:30

Figure 20 (left) Selection of the route* to be completed, (right) Display* of the day rout

MAWIS waste disposal	
▲ Kronens	1 construction place
01129 Dres	2 bad weather conditions
Ⓜ Kronens	3 bin blocked by car
(Zahnarzt)	4 various reasons
	5 free text
Kronenstr.	22 0/3
Kronenstr.	24 0/2
Kronenstr.	26 0/1
Kronenstr.	27 0/2
Kronenstr.	29 0/1
Wilder-Mann-Str.	37 0/2
0	0 / 0 24/03/10 14:00:55

Enter number of bags manually	
3	bad weather conditions 14:45
Ⓜ Kronenstr.	20 3/2
(Zahnarzt)	
Kronenstr.	22 3/5
Kronenstr.	24 1/2
Kronenstr.	26 1/1
01129 Dresden, Trachau	
Ⓜ Kronenstr.	27 0/2
bin blocked by car 14:45	
DD-XX 1234 14:46	
21 / 411	0 / 0 24/03/10 14:46:43

Figure 21 - (left) Entry of reasons* why emptying was prevented, (right) Entry of numbers of waste disposal bags

MAWIS waste disposal	
Lifter block!	
Reason: Contamination detected	
Antenna: right	
OK	
1 / 411	0 / 0 25/03/10 13:13:12

Figure 22 - (left) Display of lifter lockout triggering, (right) Navigation to job location

* If the data is available and planned in a tour (white list)

7.10 Optional Extension

The standard system is extendable by various optional equipment. The selection of this is determined by the used lifter and the wishes of end users.

7.10.1 Display of identification on the lifter:

Successful identification is displayed by means of corresponding signal units with LEDs (light boxes Figure 23) located on the respective operating side of the lifter.

Figure 23 - Light Box

7.10.2 Operating unit for entries at the rear of the vehicle:

In addition to data entry on the on-board computer, operating units are available at the lifter for the person performing the loading. The figure shows an operating unit with four buttons, each of which can be individually labelled. The lamp signals to the user that the device is ready for input and that the entry was registered successfully (Figure 24)

Figure 24 - Button box (operating unit)

7.10.3 Telephony

The telephony function allows the user to make telephone calls, the receipt of messages, the comprehensible display of call lists, use a phone book and make calls directly from the order list to the customers with the MOBA board computer Operand. Advantages besides the easy use of the large touch screen are the regulation of allowed and disallowed phone numbers. If the customers phone number exists in the order list it is easily possible to call the customer by selecting the order from the order list.

Hands-free device: The telephony package includes a hands-free device (Figure 25). The advantage is an easy connection to the board computer and a high quality audio playback.

Figure 25 - (left) Speaker, (middle) Amplifier, (right) Microphone

8 Data Communication between vehicles and Collection module

The standard interface to the database software for bin management and the mobile equipment today is the wireless data communication via GSM (2G, 3G or LTE or expected new generations).

The following chapter will explain the structure of this software platform and the functionality as an overview, because this software is operating in the background.

8.1 Data transfer – use of the MOBA internet platform (MIP)

In this variant, the data transfer to and from the vehicles works via radio transmission to the MOBA data server. On the left side are the trucks with the mobile devices. They communicate via an internet connection with the MOBA internet platform. (Middle) On the right side you can see the customer site with an example of software solution and a service-access for MOBA staff (Figure 26).

Figure 26 - Flow of data when using mobile Internet and MOBA Internet Platform (MIP)

The PC on the customer site it is necessary to install some MOBA components of the MOBA internet platform using the follow requirements:

- Windows XP, SP3 or higher
- .NET4.0 (separated install under Windows XP)
- Connect to MOBA-Server, this means a HTTPS-communication with a standard port like 10002 to the outside.

8.2 Tasks of MIP

The MIP is a server software running in the background. There is no graphical user interface integrated. The communication with connected software is managed via file contents.

The MIP is responsible for covering the following tasks:

- Transfer of route information to the truck equipment
- Send the black list and white list to the truck
- Data transfer of emptying data
- Transfer of GPS log and event triggered information to server
- Packing of FMS data and transfer to server
- Service activities for the software management like firmware download and
- Firmware configuration
- Parameter setup
- Diagnose

8.3 Data transfer is via a special USB data carrier (MemoryDrive)

Figure 27 - MOBA Memory Drive

The MOBA Memory Drive - Figure 27 - is used for backup purposes. It is an opportunity for off-line data communication in case of the wireless network is down.

The memory drive is like a USB stick, just with a special connector for higher number of connection cycles.

The counterpart RPFMAWIS software is necessary to get access to the stored data.

8.4 Avoiding data loss - data security concept

The data collection from the Identification process to the storage into a save memory in the MIP is designed and evaluated according to the “CC, Common Criteria”.

The CC is international rule for the IT system design and evaluation. It is accepted globally by governmental institutions like BSI in Germany. A list of these institutions is available here [\[6\]](#).

These countries accept based on SOG-IS the certificate from the other countries. This agreement avoids the necessity to do the certification in each country again.

The whole MAWIS system is designed with a mechanism and functionalities to avoid data losses and make any kind of manipulation transparent with a matching level of security.

The certification per CC is increasing the acceptance of the user and connected citizen significantly.

8.4.1 MOBA Operand on-board computer mechanism

The MOBA Operand on-board computer is equipped with several memory media. The plugged-in USB memory stick (Memory Drive) stores the emptying data and is based on a non-volatile FLASH. To bridge power failures, the data is also buffered in a non-volatile MRAM. Each time the system is switched on, a check is performed to determine whether this memory contains any unsaved data records; if necessary, the data is saved on the Memory Drive. Each time the system is switched off, the data is also saved on the internal flash EPROM, which is structured as a ring memory and can store route data for 90 days independent of the number of data records. For example, if a route consists of 1,500 data records, a total of 135,000 data records are stored.

Restoring lost data:

By means of a special service data carrier, data can be retrieved from the on-board computer of the vehicle using a menu-driven program. Menu for backing up route data on the on-board computer:

8.4.2 CG1 on-board computer mechanism

The CG1 vehicle equipment consists of an embedded computer that sends all emptying data to a server via the mobile phone network. The transmission path here is classified as potentially insecure. In principle, contact with the server can be lost at any time (loss of operating voltage, dropped connection, down server). This risk is countered by following the security policy:

For this purpose, the CG1 is equipped with several storage media. The storage media is based on non-volatile FLASH or FRAM technology. Using these media, all data (billing-relevant emptying data, configuration data) is backed up multiple times.

In the event of a power failure on the vehicle, the internal electronics of the CG1 continue to operate until all saved operations involving the saving of billing-relevant data on the non-volatile data memory have concluded.

Communication between the CG1 and server occurs via a secure connection that eliminates the loss and falsification of data records. If the connection to the server is lost, all emptying data collected during this time and which needs to be sent to the server is stored until the connection is re-established and the transmission is completed. The memory capacity on the vehicle is sufficient here for 400,000 emptying records. If one assumes that 2,000 data records are produced each day, a lost connection can thereby be bridged for at least 200 days.

To counter data loss on the server, the 400,000 emptying records also remain stored in a ring memory on the CG1. As a result, there remains sufficient time (several weeks) in this case as well to resolve the server problems without impacting the waste collection tours.

Diagnostic messages on both the vehicle equipment as well as at the dispatchers support secure operation of the system.

8.4.3 The MIP mechanism

The emptying file which is used in the following steps for PAYT is protected against data manipulation. The files are stored with protection keys in an archive for compare purposes in case of data loss or manipulation. The check of consistence of file is easy possible by using of a check program. The hardware and software of the data transfer channel is classified as unsure.

The security is realized about the software which is organizing the transfer. That gives the system the advantage to change the transfer channel without the need to update the certification.

9 Software developments

Waste Collection Companies ([WCC](#)) need a software tool in order to manage different tasks of the service. The solution that MOBA will provide in the Waste4Think project is the Web-Based tool Mawis U3 (nomenclature to be defined). It will be based on the existing [Mawis U2](#) whereby the dispatcher in the office can interact with the information of the service.

A set of tools are provided as a background in [Mawis U2](#). The purpose, in the context of Waste4Think, is to evolve it into Mawis U3 (or a similar name). Such evolution will bring on important improvements in terms of efficiency for the waste collection service taking into account the following aspects:

- Filling Level Sensors management and data exploitation
- Chamber system management
- Tour optimization process
- Eco-driving habits
- [PAYT](#) scheme management

Moreover, there will be an integration between MOBA and [FIWARE](#) platforms in order to share the results on the Cascais Pilot. Such integration still needs to be defined.

It is worth remarking that some of these improvements have already been applied whilst some others are still pending. Therefore, the reader will find descriptions of both deployed and upcoming developments.

In conclusion, MOBA will provide new (and renewed) IT tools to complement the hardware devices so that the [WCC](#) can reduce time, costs and emissions on the service.

9.1 Sensor Platform

The sensor platform comprises of many of the improvements performed throughout the first period of the Waste4Think. [Mawis U2](#) already worked with filling level sensors. Hence, in this section, the reader will find developments that have been made in order to improve the user performance on this field. In addition, this has a strong impact when it comes to tour optimization. It is a very important feature for the [WCC](#) to take into account the filling level data in order to avoid unnecessary journeys. It directly implies cost and emissions reduction.

9.1.1 Information from the sensors displayed on Mawis U3

On Mawis U3 one can display (in real time) the filling level of each item directly on the map (Figure 28). It can be seen on the circle drawn around, whose colour (configurable by the user) indicates the filling level. The user can also check the percentage value of the filling level using the item's popup (Figure 29).

Filling level data was already fetched into [Mawis U2](#). Notwithstanding, ever since the Waste4Think started, MOBA has introduced new features and has improved the usability of such information. Not only

that but, from a management perspective, the office dispatcher now has the opportunity to personalize how this information is shown. This is useful since it helps the user to rapidly interpret the information in a visual manner.

Figure 28 - Filling Levels of the sensors on the map

Figure 29 - Information of the sensors on the map

9.1.2 Sensors are configured and linked to a garbage bin

On the [Asset management module](#), the user can add, edit and configure features of every sensor. Previously, on [Mawis U2](#), there was no possibility for the user to modify/configure the sensors. In all the forms, MOBA has performed improvements in order to provide the user a friendlier interface and to include new possibilities.

This has brought the user more flexibility when working with the filling level sensors. Before, on [Mawis U2](#), the configuration was something fixed from the very beginning of the project and the user could not perform any customization.

9.1.2.1 Add new sensor

To add a new sensor (Figure 30), the user must open the corresponding form and set the sensor's code and the creation date and, link it to a garbage bin using the field *Item*.

MAP NEW SENSOR x

Save Cancel Exit

New sensor

MAIN DATA SETTINGS

* CODE:

* CREATION DATE: * CREATION TIME: EXPIRATION TIME: EXPIRY DATE:
23/05/2017 10:55:37

ITEM:

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

Figure 30 - Form for adding a new sensor

9.1.2.2 Edit existing sensor

To edit an existing sensor, the user must open the edit form (Figure 31), similar to the previous form (add sensor). The user can change or link a garbage bin from *Items* tab with the *Connected Items* grid.

Save Cancel Print Exit

Sensor: 15722

MAIN DATA SETTINGS ITEMS COMPANIES

ITEM	ADDRESS	FROM	TO
Biological On-Street 1100 - 00000000000000000000	Carrer Campins, 59 - Sant Celoni (Sant Celoni)	23/05/2017 09:51:26	
Clothes On-Street 2500 - 851952000249F a		04/03/2016 10:18:40	23/05/2017 09:51:26
OR0128 - 851952000454P sensor pruelias	LA RAHOLA, 89 - Barcelona (DB1)	05/04/2016 10:45:57	06/11/2016 11:33:22

Connect Edit Settings

Figure 31 - Form for editing an existing sensor

9.1.2.3 Configure features

From item's categories form (Figure 32), the user:

- Determines the properties of the sensors: *Material type, location type, bin height (cm), height (in cm) to consider a 100% filling, time between readings (min), time between transmissions (min).*
- Enable / Disable Smart mode of the sensors (if the sensor has it).
- Define the properties of every filling level. Namely, the icon, the lower/upper bound, the color and the radius of the circle drawn over the garbage bins on the map.

Save Print Exit

Category: ORG360 *

MAIN DATA SENSORS

MATERIAL TYPE: Metal LOCATION TYPE: On street

BEAN HEIGHT (CM): 100 100% FILLING (CM): 90

TIME BETWEEN READINGS (MIN): 5 TIME BETWEEN TRANSMISSIONS (MIN): 15

SMART MODE

* FILLED (%): 0 * NEARLY FILLED (%): 0 * NEARLY EMPTY (%): 0 * EMPTY (%): 0

ICON	TYPE OF SENSOR R...	LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND	COLOR	RADIUS (M)
	Filling level	0	25	White	40
	Filling level	26	50	Yellow green	40
	Filling level	51	75	Orange	40
	Filling level	76	101	Red	40

Connect Edit Disconnect Settings

Figure 32 - Form for editing an item's category

9.1.3 Sensors' information taken into account in the Tour Planning

On the background software (i.e. [Mawis U2](#), prior to applying modifications), there was only information on the reports. So, the [WCC](#) could only see the filling levels in a graphical report but could not use it. Now, it is possible to plan the tour taking into account the filling level of the garbage bins. For that purpose, Mawis U3 provides the user with a tool to filter those garbage bins whose filling level is within a range previously entered by the user.

The user can choose the action to be performed on the filtered garbage bins. This action may be:

- Add to the tour (Add button).
- Delete from the tour (Delete button).
- Highlight for easy viewing on the map (Highlight button).

The user will be able to choose whether the filter is applied to all the garbage bins of the map, only to the planned ones or only to the available ones (Figure 33 and Figure 34).

Figure 33 - Filtering options by filling level

Figure 34 - Highlight the result after applying the filter

9.1.4 Integration with [Sotkon](#) systems to retrieve chamber data

Initially, the Pilot in Cascais should have installed the chambers from MOBA. This would have implied to developing only the software part for the management. However, it was decided to change into the current chamber's provider, [Sotkon](#). The Sotkon chambers are fitted with electronic chips from EMZ and hence, MOBA will integrate its software to that of EMZ in order to provide the openings of the chambers.

The analysis of the integration for the chamber data between the MOBA platform and the [Sotkon](#) systems is still pending. [Sotkon](#) is the provider of the chambers in Cascais for this Pilot and we need to establish the parameters that need to be interchanged between the chambers and Mawis U3. This information will be used later to inform the [WCC](#) about the usage per bin of each citizen/user for the [PAYT](#) scheme.

9.2 Software Platform

Many improvements are continuously applied into the MOBA Mawis platform. The existing Mawis U2 software is evolving into Mawis U3 thanks to the W4T project. In this sense, the platform is being upgraded so that the users can speed up their daily tasks and ease their jobs.

This is the main goal of the software updates that MOBA is fetching to the web platform. In the current section, these software upgrades will be described.

9.2.1 [FIWARE](#) platform integration

[FIWARE](#) provides cloud hosting services based on OpenStack technology and a set of components offering a number of added-value functions “as a service”, the Generic Enablers (GEs). The GEs are based on open standard APIs that make it easier to connect to the Internet of Things, process data and media in real-time at large scale, perform Big Data analysis or incorporate advanced features to interact with users; [FIWARE](#) can be considered as an open alternative to existing proprietary Internet platforms.

This platform will be provided with the data requested to MOBA systems. It is still pending the analysis to define which data will be interchanged. The interconnection between both platforms will be “horizontal” which means that first, the data will be treated and stored in MOBA since it is currently using its own communications platform (the [MIP](#)). Then, the desired information will be transferred to/from the [FIWARE](#) platform so that it can be available and observable.

The figure below (Figure 35) shows the above-mentioned data flow between MOBA and [FIWARE](#).

Figure 35 - Scheme of the data interchange between MOBA and [FIWARE](#)

9.2.2 Dashboard add-ons

Mawis U3 will present its own dashboard. It will give the user a graphical display of the most important data of indicators and measures through different types of graphs and grids (widgets).

Figure 36 - Dashboard examples

The displayed data on every widget will be automatically updated without any assistance from the user. Alternatively, the user could change the refresh time and, if needed, force the refresh of the widget. There will be the possibility to change other parameters using the widget's settings. There also will exist the possibility to maximize any widget on a tab (Figure 36).

9.2.3 Sensor alerts and notifications

Mawis U3 will offer a set of alerts and notifications that will allow the user to have all the information under control without losing any details (Figure 37).

The alerts will notify the user in real time about some data that, due to its importance, requires their attention and/or a quick action.

Likewise, notifications will allow the gathering of all the information that is useful to the user. The user will be able to mainly filter, delete and mark those that have been read.

Figure 37 - Notifications/Alerts panel

9.2.4 Chamber system

The Chamber is an access control system to garbage bins with “opening by identification”. Each Chamber has access to one single garbage bin. It is not possible from a Chamber to have access to two or more garbage bins. If garbage bins are large in size, it is possible to locate more than one Chamber that allows access to it from different points.

The user who wants to throw the garbage into a bin must be identified by an [RFID](#) card (or similar) that has been assigned previously. This card works like a key so the Chamber, once the card is detected, it allows opening and, consequently, the access to the garbage bin. In this way, it is possible to have (for each user) the number of times he/she throws garbage into a certain bin and the moment he/she does it (i.e. the participation of each citizen).

9.2.4.1 Management of the chambers installed

Mawis U3 will have a new tool into the [Assets Management module](#) (Chamber Module) to manage the necessary data for its correct operation. From Mawis U3 it will be possible to add, modify and delete:

- The data related to users that utilize the Chamber System.
- The data of the identification cards that allow the Chamber’s opening (if it is authorized).

From MOBA it will be sent to each Chamber the list of IDs from the cards to control the access. Depending on the type of list (white or black), it will authorize or deny (respectively) the access to those cards whose identifiers are included in it.

Each Chamber will send MOBA the information of the accesses (services) of authorized users, indicating the day and time of each access. This data can be then managed from the Mawis U3’s Chamber module to obtain information about the amount of waste generated by each user as well as the frequency of usage.

9.2.4.2 White and/or Black lists configurations

Chambers can manage two types of lists:

- **White-lists**

White-lists include all those cards that are authorized to open the Chamber. If a card is included in this list, the Chamber will authorize the access to it.

- **Black-lists**

Black-lists include all those cards that are not authorized to open the Chamber. If a card is included in this list, the Chamber will not authorize the access.

9.2.5 [GUI](#) improvements: New [Sencha](#) migration version 6.0.2

Main improvements of Mawis U3 thanks to the migration to the new version of [Sencha](#):

- UNICODE support.
- New charts with more improvements.

o Pie 3D

The major new features in the charts package are the improvements on the 3D pie series (pie3d). It now supports labels, the legend, highlighting, tooltips, bevels and an improved shading with configurable level of 3D effect (Figure 38).

Figure 38 - 3D Pie chart example

- Incorporation of the mirroring effect (Right to Left) required in languages such as Hebrew or Arabic (Figure 39).

Figure 39 - Mirroring effect on text labels (right to left orientation)

- New controls, new properties and methods over existing ones.

9.2.5.1 Forms: New format

The Mawis U3 forms have been redesigned to offer the user a greater usability and better experience.

- Horizontal layout of the internal form tabs allowing to take more advantage of the size of the screen and easing the visualization of the information (Figure 40).

Figure 40 - Horizontal layout of the tabs within a form

- Move the toolbar onto the top of the form and increase its size to facilitate the use of the different actions (Figure 41).

Figure 41 - New toolbars within the forms

- Inclusion of the print button that allows direct printing without having to access the reporting module (Figure 42).

Figure 42 - Print button within the forms

- Inclusion of an orange-coloured border (Figure 43, left) to indicate the active form at that moment. The border changes to red when the user makes any changes to the form (Figure 43, right).

Figure 43 - (left) Active form is marked with an orange border, (right) Changes made in a form mark the tab in red

- Largest caption of the form and it includes an icon (Figure 44).

Figure 44 - New captions with icons

- Possibility to access the desired form or to close them all on the drop-down button in the upper right corner of the form (Figure 45).

Figure 45 - Drop-down button to select/close the desired forms

- The maps in the forms can be extended to full-screen mode thus, facilitating their visualization (Figure 46 and Figure 47).

Figure 46 - Button to make the map full-screen size

Figure 47 - Full-screen mode activated

9.2.5.2 Hyperlinked objects in the website

Another useful upgrade within the W4T is that many of the object in the website are hyperlinked. Meaning that you can rapidly navigate to one specific object. For instance, now, when the user runs the History option for a device in the Fleet Management module to print the service tour performed by one truck, the objects have a hyperlink. Consequently, the user can retrieve data from one specific collected bin or any exception raised throughout the tour by just one single click (Shift + Left mouse button click).

This feature saves a notorious amount of time to the user making the navigation through the different modules of the application easier. For example, you might want to check some details or the last collections of one bin and, instead of looking for it in the searching options, you can click on the icon on the map and go straight to its records (as shown in Figure 48 Figure 48 - Hyperlinked objects. Bin information access from the map icon.).

Figure 48 - Hyperlinked objects. Bin information access from the map icon.

9.3 Waste Collection Optimization

Amongst the main functionalities of the [Mawis U2](#) software, one can find the Tour Planning module. This tool gives the user (the office dispatcher) the possibility to plan the tours of the trucks beforehand. It brings multiple benefits to the [WCC](#) in terms of time and fuel consumption, plus, on the other hand, the emissions can be lessened.

One of the points in this project is to provide improvements on this Tour planning module. Hence, the ongoing Mawis U3 has included and will include a set of new functionalities and enhancements in order to upraise the performance in this area. The main modifications included so far are focused on the Online Operation control monitoring (see [9.3.1.1](#)), the Service Scheduling (see [9.3.1.2](#)) and different upgrades to facilitate the user's tasks and make the steps it faster (see [9.3.1.6](#), [9.3.1.9](#), [9.3.1.10](#) and [9.3.1.11](#)).

9.3.1 Enhanced Tour Planning

9.3.1.1 Online operation control monitoring

This control provides a Widget to control the fulfilment of scheduled services through the Service Schedule during the last 24 hours (maximum). The displayed data are refreshed periodically. This screen has a run selector at the top and a results grid (Figure 49).

9.3.1.1.1 Run selector

In the upper panel of the screen, one can select which elements will be displayed in the Widget and the fraction of time that is going to be displayed. The selectable values are:

- **Modality:** It allows to select one or more modes (indicated in the tour models that were active in the last 24 hours and visible by the user) and it is used to restrict the data to be displayed in the results table.

- **Tour model:** It allows to select one or more active route models (in the last 24 hours and visible to the user). When a Mode is selected, only the tour models that have that mode will be selected. The selection will be used to restrict the data to be displayed in the results table.
- **Time:** It allows to indicate the time back from the current time, which will be used to obtain the schedules that will be shown in the results table. The time that can be indicated will be between 00:00:00 and 23:59:59. If 00:00:00 is indicated, only the current schedules will be displayed. Otherwise, if it is 23:59:59, there will be displayed all the schedules that have been active in the last 24 hours.
- **Start:** This button activates the automatic calculation of the results table when it is pressed. The values in the selection panel that are required for the calculation, are blocked while the automatic update of the results table is active. The results table is updated periodically according to the values configured by the user. This value must be greater than 1 minute.
- **Stop:** This button stops the automatic calculation of the results table. The selection panel values that that are required for the calculation, are unlocked so that they can be modified.

9.3.1.1.2 The results table

The results table shows those settings that meet the conditions indicated in the upper panel. The data shown are updated periodically according to the time indicated in the parameterization of the user who is launching it. The values shown in the results table are:

- **Tour Model:** Shows the tour model code and his description (format: Code - Description).
- **Shift date:** Shows the date/time of the schedule shift start.
- **Shift:** Shows the shift code assigned to that schedule.
- **Vehicle:** Shows the vehicle registration number assigned to the shift.
- **Modality:** Shows the modality indicated in the tour model.
- **Tour Start:** Shows the tour start date.
- **Tour End:** Shows the tour end date.
- **Tour Accomplishment:** Shows the percentage of the comparison between planned tour points in the tour model with respect to those made by the vehicle of that schedule.
- **Bins Performed:** Shows the percentage of elements operated in relation to the planned ones and the absolute number. If it has been operating in the schedule (start and end of tour exist), a hyperlink is enabled that opens the list "Detail of Elements by Tour", associated with the schedule data. The list shows the planned items collected, the planned items not collected and the items not planned. On can select the output format of the report (pdf, csv or xls).
- **E.W.T. (Effective Work Time):** Shows the effective working time of the vehicle in that schedule (Final Tour - Start Tour).
- **Sequence Accomplishment:** Shows the percentage of compliance of the order of operation of planned elements with respect to how the elements have been operated by the vehicle in that schedule.
- **Mile:** It shows the total kilometres made by the vehicle in that schedule.
- **Map:** It is a button that launches the map. This map shows information about the planned tour model and what the vehicle has done in the schedule.
- **Effective work started:** Shows the date/time of the first planned action performed (planned operated element or planned tour point operated) by the vehicle in that schedule. If no planned action has been taken it will not be informed.

- **Effective work finished:** Shows the date/time of the last scheduled action performed (planned operated element or planned tour point operated) by the vehicle in that schedule. If no planned action has been taken it will not be informed.

Figure 49 - Run selector and the results table

9.3.1.2 Service scheduling

This control allows to schedule services assigning vehicles for each shift and a service type of a given tour. This control has a filter and a table that shows the information of the scheduled services (Figure 50).

- **Filter**

It is located at the top of the screen. It allows to select the values: company, tour model, shift, service type and vehicle that will be the filtered on the scheduled services shown in the table below.

- **Results table**

This table allows to visualize all the services scheduled for a specific day that the user can choose through the date control located above it. In addition to displaying the information, this table is editable allowing to assign the vehicles to each route for each shift and service type, using a drop-down that appears when clicking on any line of the table in the vehicle column and showing all vehicles that can be assigned.

The user has the possibility to apply the schedule of a specific day to other days periodically, using the Frequency button next to the date control.

The Save button on the form will save schedules made on different days or on the same day. It can also record a specific schedule by pressing the pencil icon in the Save column.

Figure 50 - Filters and result table of the scheduled services

9.3.1.3 Incidences reported by citizens by App (T4.5)

It is necessary to do the integration analysis of the App (T4.5) and the MOBA platform.

9.3.1.4 Vehicle properties and availability

This is something to be analysed. The tour planning may take into account the vehicle properties, such as:

- Dimensions of the vehicle.
- Loading type (side, rear ...).
- Autonomy.

9.3.1.5 Driver properties and availability

This is something to be analysed. The tour planning may take into account the driver properties, such as:

- Schedules.
- Driving License type (if applicable).
- Sick leave.

9.3.1.6 Calendar

The Scheduling control allows to scheduling the services of each Tour Model assigning the available vehicles on the existing shifts and selected days. Likewise, to expedite this assignment, it is possible to

Deliverable D2.5

periodically apply the assignments of a specific day until a specific date and selecting the days of the week (Monday, Tuesday, etc.) by means of a calendar (Figure 51).

This control not only allows to create schedules in each Tour Model (assigning vehicles in the available shifts), but also to modify and to delete the already existing assignments.

Figure 51 - Calendar of the services tours

New features on the middle processes (i.e. the forms) have been renovated in the calendar tool. The intention, as always, is to ease the user's job on the process (Figure 52)

Figure 52 - Renovated forms within the calendar options

9.3.1.7 Time restrictions

It is going to be analysed the possibility of taking into account the time restrictions at the moment of planning the tour, such as:

- Schools schedules (kids leaving the school).
- Road works.
- Sport activities.
- Popular festivals.
- Demonstrations (protests).

9.3.1.8 Traffic data

It will be analysed the possibility of taking into account the traffic forecast at the moment of planning the tour. From the estimations of the volume of traffic in certain time slots, one could avoid the more collapsed slots and thus, optimize the services programmed in a tour (Figure 53).

Figure 53 - Traffic data

9.3.1.9 Grids multi-select

This control allows the multi-selection of items (Figure 54). This consists of two tables, one above the other. The upper one shows the currently selected items; the lower one shows the available items (except for those that are already selected). Between the two tables there are buttons:

- To transfer items from one to another. Moreover, it is possible to transfer them through drag & drop or double click on the item.
- To show/hide the available items table.

The selected items table have buttons to change the order of the selected items.

The available items table have a button for reloading.

The first time this control is loaded, only the selected items table is shown; the available items table is hidden and not loaded.

Tour model: 000001 TOUR 0001SD

MAIN DATA DISTRICTS CATEGORIES ITEMS MAP VEHICLES SCHEDULING COMPANIES

SELECTED	CODE	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	FILLING LEVEL	REQUESTS	STREET	DISTRICT	TOWN	FROM	LOCATI...	ADDITIONAL IN...
1	000000341P	ORG120	000000341		41	PG. JOAN DE BORBO C. D...	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Charfe...	
2	000000280P	ORG120	000000280		83	C. PETXINA, 3	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Sweet ...	
3	000000087P	ORG120	000000087		91	C. OCATA, 4	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	La Estr...	
4	000000185P	ORG120	000000185		1	VIA LAIETANA, 32	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Starbu...	
5	000000192P	ORG120	000000192		12	C. FRIKCESA, 16	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Nou Ce...	
6	000000422P	ORG120	000000422		58	PG. JOAN DE BORBO C. D...	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Rte. N...	
7	000000457P	ORG120	000000457		24	VIA LAIETANA, 32	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Starbu...	
8	000000539P	ORG120	000000539		76	C. DUANA, 4	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Reside...	
9	000000806P	ORG120	000000806		77	VIA LAIETANA, 40	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	VIA LA...	
10	000000815P	ORG120	000000815		68	VIA LAIETANA, 46	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	Rosa N...	
11	000000404P	ORG120	000000404		55	LA RAMBLA, 71	D01	Barcelona	23/05/2017 10:28...	LA RA...	

AVAILABLE	CODE	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	LOCATION NAME	FILLING LEVEL	REQUESTS	STREET	DISTRICT	TOWN	ADDITIONAL INFORMATI...
1	000000008P	ORG800	000000008	Carrefour		6	LA RAMBLA, 113	D01	Barcelona	
2	000000022P	ORG120	000000022	LA RAMBLA 125		2	LA RAMBLA, 125	D01	Barcelona	
3	000000028P	ORG120	000000028	LA RAMBLA 127		0	LA RAMBLA, 127	D01	Barcelona	
4	000000029P	ORG120	000000029	LA RAMBLA 127		0	LA RAMBLA, 127	D01	Barcelona	
5	000000030P	ORG120	000000030	LA RAMBLA 127		0	LA RAMBLA, 127	D01	Barcelona	
6	000000031P	ORG120	000000031	LA RAMBLA 127		0	LA RAMBLA, 127	D01	Barcelona	
7	000000032P	ORG120	000000032	LA RAMBLA 127		0	LA RAMBLA, 127	D01	Barcelona	
8	000000041P	ORG120	000000041	AV. PARAL·LEL 38		0	AV. PARAL·LEL, 38	D01	Barcelona	
9	000000050P	ORG90	000000050	Casa Defin		75	PG. BORN, 36	D01	Barcelona	
10	000000055P	ORG90	000000055	PG. BORN 34		0	PG. BORN, 34	D01	Barcelona	
11	000000063P	ORG120	000000063	PL. DE LES OLLES 3		0	PL. DE LES OLLES, 3	D01	Barcelona	
12	000000065P	ORG120	000000065	Cafe de la Ribera		15	PL. DE LES OLLES, 6	D01	Barcelona	
13	000000085P	ORG120	000000085	C. MARQUESA 1		0	C. MARQUESA, 1	D01	Barcelona	
14	000000098P	ORG120	000000098	Rincon de la Ciudadela		0	C. COMERÇ, 19	D01	Barcelona	

Figure 54 - Grid multi-select example

9.3.1.10 Master Tour in cache

In previous versions of [Mawis U2](#) there were controls, such as map, scheduling and multi-select grids, which had their own save button and only saved their own values. Likewise, the forms' save button saved the value of the other controls except the controls mentioned above. This prevented the user to work in cache memory and to be able to restore the form to its initial state recovering the initial values of each one of the controls.

In the current version of Mawis U3, all the changes made in the form, remain in memory and the form save button can save all the controls values.

9.3.1.11 Improvements on the performance

Dependencies between controls have been implemented and it allows them to update their value depending on the value of another control. In tour models there are dependencies between the grid multi-select of items and the map, which allow the planned items to be equal on both parts, on the map and on the grid multi-select of the planned items. Hence, any change on the planned items in one control, is updated in the other.

9.3.1.12 Eco-driving: Analyse the feasibility of including the [FMS](#) (Fleet Management System) data to help the company to improve/control the driving habits

Among the gathered data within a service tour, it is interesting to know the behaviour of the driver. For such purpose, the vehicles have the possibility to inform of some parameters from their engine. Namely, these parameters are known as Fleet Management System ([FMS](#)) data.

Figure 55 - FMS-Standard icon

Although there is an [FMS](#) standard (Figure 55), one can find some variations depending on the truck. Not all the trucks allow to fetch the same information which makes it difficult to establish a certain standard. Nevertheless, usually it is possible to obtain the basic parameters for the fuel consumption and the velocity. [Mawis U2](#) is able to report the collected data so that the Waste Collection Company is provided with useful information in order to foster and improve the eco-driving habits.

In addition, on Mawis U3 it will be analysed the possibility of including these parameters into the Enhanced Tour planning process. Such task can become quite hard due to the variation between trucks and the amount of necessary data for a reasonable outcome. Meaning that, in order to achieve trustworthy values, one needs to feed the system with huge amounts of data (i.e. [FMS](#) extractions every single second) to be sure not to lose any important detail on the tour. Besides, one may have different parameters amongst the fleet that makes the comparison unfair. The intention of this analysis is to study the feasibility of including this information into consideration at the time of planning the service tours. For instance, one could decide between different vehicles when it comes to an urban area instead of a suburban one and vice versa based on the fuel consumption of each one (Figure 56).

Figure 56 - Fetching the FMS data from the truck's engine into the databases to use it on the software either in reports or optimization of a service tour

On the on-board computers, it will be also analysed the possibility to add feedback to the drivers in order to help them follow the good driving habits and hence, reduce the gas emissions.

9.3.2 Hardware-Software integration improvements

Mawis U3 will be the web application that gives the office clerks the necessary tools to control and manage the tasks of the Waste Collection Service. For that purpose, the databases are interconnected with the on-board computers on the trucks.

With the intent of facilitating and speeding up some of the tasks that affect both sides, the software and the hardware, MOBA has implemented some improvements in that area. Hence, the forthcoming Mawis U3 presents enhanced tools for the Waste Collection Companies to reduce efforts and time.

9.3.2.1 FollowMe improvements

The Follow Me is a tool of the MOBA's on-board computer that allows to record the "ideal" tour by means of an experimented driver. Later, when a new driver needs to fulfil that route, he/she just need to load that Follow Me file and follow the instructions.

Until now, the master files were generated from the tour recorded by the vehicles. This file could not be edited and, any modification involved re-recording the tour from the vehicle. It was not practical and it arose the need to be able to edit the files from [Mawis U2](#). Not just to modify them, but to be able to generate them without having to save them from the vehicle (Figure 57). This is now included in the upcoming Mawis U3.

Figure 57 - Importing and editing a FollowMe tour file directly on the web

9.3.2.1.1 Unique file integration

Previously, a master file was required for each tour, vehicle and day, which brought the need to create many files. For example, to plan the tour of 5 vehicles in 10 days, it was necessary to generate 50 files, one file per vehicle and day. To avoid having to generate so many files, at first it was decided to generate them to schedule only one week. Then, every week, these files were generated again and the old ones were deleted. Finally, as the contents of these files were the same for each tour, MOBA has chosen to reuse the same file for different days and vehicles, which allows a greater optimization of the system resources.

9.3.2.1.2 Auto-importing

Initially, to import the master files it was necessary to use the *Memory Drive* that is connected to the *Operand* (on-board computer) of the vehicle. This implied that, once the tour was finished and recorded in the *Memory Drive*, it had to be connected to the corresponding computer and import the data to [Mawis U2](#).

This procedure is not optimal for quick import of the master files on the software. This is the reason that led MOBA to create a new method to send the file directly from the Operand to a file manager of MOBA. Later, it will be requested by the application Mawis U3, from where the user can choose between the different master files and then import one (Figure 58).

Figure 58 - Before the data was fetched manually from the Memory Drive. Now this data can be imported directly from the on-board computer to the system

9.3.2.2 Adapt the system to new features of the mini-Operand and the [MIP](#) platform

MOBA is developing the mini-Operand, a new device with similar Operand (existing device) features but with the advantage of being portable and smaller. To guarantee its correct performance, it is necessary to check if any changes are required on the software part. This analysis will be made at the corresponding time and it can become an easy task or a hard one, depending on the new features.

10 Architecture

Hereafter a brief description together with a schematic picture in order shortly detail the systems' architecture in MOBA. By systems' architecture we understand the backbone structure of the IT (Information Technology) systems in order to manage the data interchange and exploitation.

All data from the Waste Collection service is stored into databases so that the office's clerks can retrieve the necessary reports and perform the consequent analyses.

The data generated by different sensors (either vehicle sensors or mobile applications) is not fetched directly to the databases. Both, the users from the web application and the devices used in the service, need to go through intermediate layers. For the formers, MOBA implements a layer with [Web Services](#) for such purpose, integrated in an architecture with several depth levels and scalable (both vertically and horizontally) based on the necessity. Such [Web Services](#) allow the office clerk to get the requested data from the database as long as the user credentials are validated on the user access control layer.

On the other side, the devices send data to the communication servers (COMM servers in the figure) in various ways depending on each type of device. Some of them access directly to the servers while the MOBA on-board computers go through the [MIP](#) server (MOBA's middleware platform) under the [ViViVerse](#) protocol. Then, the [Web Services](#) come into play in order to transmit the information into the communication servers. Consequently, all data coming from or going to the on-board computers can be transferred to or from the web application, respectively. Analogous to the web application users, every device that tries to reach MOBA's datacentre is subjected to an access control.

In order to graphically describe the above-mentioned architecture, the following diagram shows the principal components that compose such structure (Figure 59).

Finally, the data storage in MOBA fulfils the national law at every level in terms of security. The MOBA MAWIS system is a system using Approved assessments and criteria "Information Technology Evaluation Criteria (ITSEC)" and "Common Criteria". The BSI "The Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik" regulates and licenses granted data security for products, components and systems. The Common Criteria and ITSEM / ITSEC Certification of MAWIS MOBA system includes the whole system data from the vehicle to office software. This certificate guarantees that there is no possibility of data manipulation to provide a certificate for the legal use in commercial transactions. In addition, MOBA stores all the data in a specialized Data Centre that meets the requirements of the category the TIER III. Finally, for the integrations with other platforms, MOBA uses the secured Web Services technology (for instance, by means of https connection and user authentication).

Figure 59 - Structure of the MOBA systems

11 Real Data from the installed devices in Cascais

The current scenario in Cascais already contains the systems from MOBA together with the chambers from Sotkon. Specifically, the fleet of Cascais is provided with the Operand on-board computer, the identification control unit (as shown in 7.5.1) and the [RFID](#) antennas. Additionally, some of the bins are fitted with Filling Level Sensors to provide real-time percentage of waste.

Consequently, such electronics components allow EMAC to gather GPS information from the truck, the location and the time of the collections, to identify the type of waste that has been collected at any time and to know the level of waste within the bins in order to optimise the routes. Shall any incidence raise during the collection service, it can be notified too. Likewise, the on-board computer allows the drivers to follow the proper route provided by the office (via the [MAWIS](#) web platform).

In the current section some data will be presented in order to demonstrate the correct performance of the system. Additionally, it will help the reader to understand how the information can be used by the [WCC](#).

11.1 Truck Data: GPS Tracking

Figure 60 shows the GPS trace of a vehicle currently used in Cascais for the Selective Collection (recyclable waste). The on-board computer sends the data via a GPRS connection so that the office clerk can check it out on the web platform over the map.

Figure 60 - GPS trace of a vehicle in Cascais

Besides, the same information can be seen on a report. Although the map visualization is a lot more user-friendly, the report can help the company in case they need to integrate that information to an

external software. The report can be exported into CSV format for that purpose. In addition, it may help identifying specific data for a specific section.

The user must select the data to be reported in the input form shown below in Figure 61. In that form the user specifies the output format (PDF, Excel or CSV), the date and time window and the list of vehicles or events to be presented.

Figure 61 - Input data selection to be shown in the report

The following figures show a list of positions within a time period (Figure 62) and a list of the events selected in the input form (Figure 63), respectively. The example has been chosen to be PDF.

 Report of Detailed Tour by Vehicle

Filter values	
From date :	04/04/2018 00:00:00
To date :	04/04/2018 23:59:59

Vehicle : 90-AT-95 (Cascais Ambiente / Seletiva)					
Date	Event	Event details	Address	Speed	Distance (mi.)
04/04/2018 00:00:03	Position		Rua Casa d'Água 12 Cascais, Lisboa	22 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:05	Position		Rua Casa d'Água 12 Cascais, Lisboa	13 mph	0.01 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:06	Position		Rua Casa d'Água 12 Cascais, Lisboa	14 mph	0.01 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:09	Position		Rua Casa d'Água 12 Cascais, Lisboa	24 mph	0.03 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:10	Position		Rua das Roseiras Cascais, Lisboa	28 mph	0.04 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:13	Position		Rua Casa d'Água Cascais, Lisboa	19 mph	0.05 Mi
04/04/2018 00:00:14	Position		Rua Varela Silva 9 Cascais, Lisboa	19 mph	0.06 Mi

Figure 62 - Example of the GPS positions within a specific time window in PDF format

Vehicle : 90-AT-95 (Cascais Ambiente / Seletiva)					
Date	Event	Event details	Address	Speed	Distance (mi.)
04/04/2018 19:16:54	Collection	Tag:5EDBCD0A00000000, lb:0	Rua Victor Hugo Moreira 12 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:21:20	Filling level (loc.)		Rua dos Girassóis 100 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:21:20	Filling level (loc.)		Rua dos Girassóis 100 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:21:20	Filling level (loc.)		Rua dos Girassóis 100 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:21:26	Collection	Tag:38D9CD0A00000000, lb:0	Rua dos Girassóis 100 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:23:43	Collection	Tag:CADBCD0A00000000, lb:0	Rua Humberto Delgado 353 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi
04/04/2018 19:23:44	Collection	Tag:CADBCD0A00000000, lb:0	Rua Humberto Delgado 353 Cascais, Lisboa	0 mph	0 Mi

Figure 63 - Example of the selected events within a specific time window in PDF format

11.2 Collections

Likewise, the collections (registered thanks to the transponders on the bins and the [RFID](#) antennas on the trucks) can be seen in a map or report view. Thanks to the link between the [RFID](#) transponder and the bins within the database, the system knows which bins have been collected. Thanks to the GPS antenna of the on-board computer it is also fetched the position of each collection. It can be later used to check whether a bin has been moved from its theoretical location.

An example of the map view would be the plotted below in Figure 64:

Figure 64 - Collections seen on the map

Another interesting outputs included thanks to the W4T project are the statistics graphs. For instance, each bin fitted with a transponder allows the user to obtain the collections' summary of the past 6 months as it is pictured in Figure 65.

Figure 65 - Statistic graph of the collections in the last 6 months for a specific bin

11.3 Incidences/Exceptions

An important upgrade in Cascais has been the automation for solving the exceptions (incidences). Mainly, they deal with 2 types of exceptions; bulky and green waste. Before, they were solving them by means of paper reporting.

Now, they use the Mawis system to deal with them. They create such exceptions on the route by means of the on-board computers. Once a driver sees some bulky or green waste, he or she registers an exception and send it to the office. Then, the Mawis user can gather the exceptions within a tour file and send it to the appropriate on-board computer so that they can go and solve them.

The mechanism is quite similar to that of the selective collections. However, these tour files are temporary (in fact, they are for one-use only) because the exceptions are always different while the collection tours tend to be periodic with occasional changes. In Figure 66, one can see how the exceptions can be seen on the map. The second step in the office would be to plan all the exceptions that have to be solved together within one tour file. This can be seen in .

The screenshot shows the MAWIS U2 interface with a map of a city area. A blue route is overlaid on the map, representing a service tour. A popup window titled 'Monstruos' provides details for a bulky waste exception:

- Date: 06/04/2018
- Time: 08:36:24
- Localization: Alagoa
- Number: 293
- City: Cascais
- State: Lisboa
- Country: Portugal
- Latitude: 38.6947784423828
- Longitude: -9.33880605969238
- Transponder: 518839
- Weight: 241 241
- Lifter: 518839
- Plan tour: 82 MT Cir. 01 - Zona 2
- Tour Start: 06/04/2018 05:18:44
- Tour End: 06/04/2018 10:38:21
- Operator: Domingos Rodrigues Rebelo
- Internal reference: 518839
- External Reference: Incidencia OFU - Objetos fora Uso
- Type: Solved
- Status: Solved
- Ticket date: 06/04/2018 08:36:24
- Description: OFU - Objetos fora Uso
- Resolution date: 06/04/2018 08:36:28
- Solved description: Solved
- Resolution picture: Solved

On the right side, there is an 'INFORMATION FILTER' section with date and time filters, and a 'POSITION DATA' section showing vehicle and event details.

Figure 66 - Exceptions for bulky waste registered in a Service Tour

The screenshot shows the MAWIS U2 interface with a table listing tickets included in a service tour model. The table has the following columns: ID, TYPE, MODEL, TASK, TICKET DESC., CREATION DATE, SOURCE, MAKER, ADDRESS, EXTERNAL RE., LINK, LINK DETAIL, ZONE, TOUR, EXTERN 3, FROM.

ID	TYPE	MODEL	TASK	TICKET DESC.	CREATION DATE	SOURCE	MAKER	ADDRESS	EXTERNAL RE.	LINK	LINK DETAIL	ZONE	TOUR	EXTERN 3	FROM
1	524,341	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	NUÑO JESUS	Pedido PHC n. 18/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Rua Dom Fua...	619405			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
2	524,332	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	Eco Jardins	Pedido PHC n. 18/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Avenida Mem...	619444			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
3	524,333	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	ABEL BOTELHO	Pedido PHC n. 18/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Rua Martin S...	619447			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
4	524,325	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	PERFLORA - ...	Pedido PHC n. 18/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Avenida da D...	619261			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
5	524,986	CJ - Cortes d...	Tour exception		19/04/2018 2.	Mawis U2	Utilizador Ver...	Rua Dom Lu...				Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
6	524,987	CJ - Cortes d...	Tour exception		19/04/2018 2.	Mawis U2	Utilizador Ver...	Rua Dom Lu...				Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
7	524,330	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	Rosa Onorio	Pedido PHC n. 18/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Estrada dos B...	619392			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2
8	522,759	Cortes Jardim	Incidenca ex.	MARJO CARV...	Pedido PHC n. 16/04/2018 1.	Vehicle	Usuario Dum...	Rua Nossa Se...	618668			Zona 2	Circuito 05	20/04/2018 0...	19/04/2018 2

Figure 67 - List of tickets included in one tour

An important feature when planning services tours for exceptions, is the automatic assignment of certain types of tickets. Meaning that, every time a ticket of that type is registered it is added automatically to that tour model. This feature is shown in Figure 68.

The screenshot shows the MAWIS U2 interface with a table listing ticket types and their automatic assignment to a tour model. The table has the following columns: CODE, MODEL, DESCRIPTION, FROM, and AUTOMATIC ASSIGNATION.

CODE	MODEL	DESCRIPTION	FROM	AUTOMATIC ASSIGNATION
1 04.02.2.05	Incidenca externa		20/03/2018 09:56:01	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Automatic assignment
2 CJ - Cortes de Jardins	Tour exception		20/03/2018 09:56:01	<input type="checkbox"/>
3 Cortes Jardim (PHC)	Incidenca externa		20/03/2018 09:56:01	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 68 - Automatic assignment of the tickets to a tour

11.4 Filling Level Sensors

In Cascais Ambiente they use an external software to manage the tickets. Hence, MOBA had integrated its platform to that external one. For that reason, the sensors do not present the filling level results in a typical percentage scale but with values within the range 1-5 (considering ranges of 20% per each of them. For instance, 0-20% → 1, 20-40% →2, etc.). In the next Figure 69, it is shown the evolution of the filling level of a certain bin.

Sensor readings by customer Report

Filter values

From date : 15/04/2018 00:00:00

To date : 20/04/2018 23:59:59

Customer : Municipio Cascais

Category: IND3000
Item code: 00000614

Date	Code	Reading type	Reading	Street	#	District	Town
15/04/2018 10:20:54	f0627f78cec248bz	Filling level	3	Rua das Rosas	10690	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775
16/04/2018 08:20:53	f0627f78cec248bz	Filling level	1	Rua das Rosas	10690	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775
19/04/2018 10:20:41	f0627f78cec248bz	Filling level	4	Rua das Rosas	10690	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775
19/04/2018 16:20:40	f0627f78cec248bz	Filling level	5	Rua das Rosas	10690	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775

Figure 69 - Sensor readings

What is really useful for the office clerk is to use that information in order to plan the collection tours based on those filling levels. It spares money and time to the company when the truck can avoid the trip to an empty bin. Below a planning example of a tour taking into account the filling levels in Figure 70.

AVI/LABE	CODE	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION	LOCATION NAME	FILLING LEVEL	REQUESTS	DESIRED DATE	STREET	DISTRICT	TOWN	ADDITIONAL INFORM.
1	000006651	IND3000	000006651	Rotunda União Europeia		Ascending order		Rua de Luxemburgo 1...	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775	1701480
2	000006669	IND3000	000006669	Nº 225		Descending order		Rua da Alemanha 106...	Lombos Sul	Carcavelos-2775	1701470
3	006859	IND3000	006859	Traseiras C.G.D		Columns		Rua Carlos Ribeiro 70...	Cascais	Cascais-2750	
4	006877	IND3000	006877	Condomínio da Cidadela		Group by this field		Avenida 25 de Abril 9...	Cascais	Cascais-2750	
5	006886	IND3000	006886	Pastelaria Cidadela		Show in groups		Rua Doutor Iracy Doyl...	Cascais	Cascais-2750	
6	006887	IND3000	006887	Sapataria Guimarães		Filter	< 5	Avenida Marginal 90430	Cascais	Cascais-2750	
7	006993	IND3000	006993	Câmara Municipal			> 3	Largo Cinco de Outub...	Cascais	Cascais-2750	

Figure 70 - Filtering the bins with the filling level between 3 and 5 in a list view

Likewise, the filtering option can be used in a map view. See Figure 71.

Figure 71 - Filtering the bins with the filling level between 3 and 5 in a map view

Annex 1

Transponder Puck U for the chip nest of DIN plastic containers
HDX transponder (with ferrite core) Figure 72 - Puck U

Figure 72 - Puck U

- Manufacturer: MOBA
- Raw transponder manufacturer: Texas Instruments
- Current* designation: RI-TRP-0105-30
- Frequency: 134.2 kHz
- Transmission method: HDX (half-duplex, frequency modulated)
- Raw transponder design: tube shape, length 23 mm, glass encapsulated
- Packaging design: plastic puck M 30 x 14, thread M 30 x 1.5
- Alignment in the chip nest: necessary
- Service life: verified for more than 10 years
- Reading range: approx. 20 cm in practical use
- Perm. temperature range: in operation - 25°C to + 85°C
- Failure rate per year: < 0.02% per year
- Risk of reading errors: The risk of reading errors is minimized by the large reading range available with this transponder. Nevertheless, if a reading cannot be performed correctly, a CRC checksum sent by the transponder ensures that incorrectly read data is rejected and is not stored in the vehicle.

* The manufacturer's product designation is changed from time to time for various reasons, e.g., the most recent change with the introduction of the ROHS directive. Thus, you may find this transponder listed in the documentation and certificates from MOBA under different designations. In any case, these are transponders with the exact same specifications and properties.

*** or ALTERNATIVELY ***

HDX transponder in puck case (air-core coil)
Figure 73 - Puck L HDX

Figure 73 - Puck L HDX

- Manufacturer: MOBA MobileAutomation AG
- Raw transponder manufacturer: Texas Instruments
- Current* designation: RI-INL-W007-40
- Frequency: 134.2 kHz
- Transmission method: HDX (half-duplex, frequency modulated)
- Raw transponder design: air-core coil, molded
- Packaging design: plastic puck M 30 x 14, thread M 30 x 1.5
- Alignment in the chip nest: not necessary
- Service life: at least 8 years
- Reading range: approx. 10 cm in practical use
- Perm. temperature range: in operation - 25°C to + 85°C
- Failure rate per year: < 0.1% per year
- Manipulation security: EEPROM lock bit
- Protection class: IP67
- Mechanical shock: EN60068-2-27, Test Ea, 3 ms, 200 g, sinusoidal half wave, 6 pulses in each direction and 2 axes
- Vibration: EN60068-2-6, Test Fc, 10 g, 10-500 Hz, 2 axes, 10 pulses per axis
- Risk of read errors: If a reading cannot be performed correctly, a CRC checksum sent by the transponder ensures that incorrectly read data is rejected and is not stored in the vehicle.

* The manufacturer's product designation is changed from time to time for various reasons, e.g., the most recent change with the introduction of the ROHS directive. Thus, you may find this transponder listed in the documentation and certificates from MOBA under different designations. In any case, these are transponders with the exact same specifications and properties.

Transponder for 4-wheel containers made of metal (belly mounting) – model Puck 1.1
Figure 74 - Puck 1.1

If these are lifted by means of folding arms, i.e., distance to antenna up to approx. 20 cm

Figure 74 - Puck 1.1

- Manufacturer: MOBA
- Raw transponder manufacturer: Texas Instruments
- Current* designation: RI-TRP-0108-30
- Frequency: 134.2 kHz
- Transmission method: HDX (half-duplex, frequency modulated)
- Raw transponder design: tube shape, length 32 mm, glass encapsulated
- Packaging design: plastic puck d=50 mm, h=15 mm
- Service life: verified operation for more than 10 years
- Reading range: approx. 40 cm in practical use
- Perm. temperature range: in operation - 25°C to + 85°C
Storage temperature - 40°C to + 100°C
- Failure rate per year: < 0.02% per year
- Risk of reading errors: The risk of reading errors is minimized by the large reading range available with the HDX transmission method. Nevertheless, if a reading cannot be performed correctly, a CRC checksum sent by the transponder ensures that incorrectly read data is rejected and is not stored in the vehicle.

* The manufacturer's product designation is changed from time to time for various reasons, e.g., the most recent change with the introduction of the ROHS directive. Thus, you may find this transponder listed in the documentation and certificates from MOBA under different designations. In any case, these are transponders with the exact same specifications and properties.

Transponder for 4-wheel containers made of metal (belly mounting)

Figure 75 - High-Performance-Transponder

If these are picked up by gripping equipment with distance to antenna of approx. 20 cm

Figure 75 - High-Performance-Transponder

- Manufacturer: MOBA
- Compatibility: with Texas Instruments RI-TRP-R9VS
- Frequency: 134.2 kHz
- Transmission method: HDX (half-duplex, frequency modulated)
- Design: oval, on fitting panel 105 mm x 60 mm x 20 mm
- Service life: no long-term experience yet exists
- Reading range: approx. 50 cm in practical use
- Perm. temperature range: in operation - 25°C to + 70°C
Storage temperature - 40°C to + 85°C
- Failure rate per year: no long-term experience yet exists
- Risk of reading errors: The risk of reading errors is minimized by the large reading range available with the HDX transmission method. Nevertheless, if a reading cannot be performed correctly, a CRC checksum sent by the transponder ensures that incorrectly read data is rejected and is not stored in the vehicle.

Annex 2

Figure 76 - LogiScann 600.

The 600 hand-held scanner is used for the data connection of transponder, bin and location for the master data base.

Figure 76 - LogiScann 600

- Manufacturer: aitronic GmbH
- Operating temperature: -20 °C to 50 °C
- Dimensions: 227 x 60 x 40 mm
- Weight: 430 g (varies depending on features)
- Display: graphic, LCD, 128 x 64 pixels, illuminated
- Keyboard: 22 buttons (alphanumeric)
- Data memory: 1 MB flash, 155 kByte RAM
- Program memory: 384 kByte
- Functions: mobile display, transponder identification, bar code identification, entry and storage of data
- Power supply: Li-Po battery 3.6 V, 1000 mAh, fast charging
- Interfaces: RS232
- Options: GPS module for recording GPS coordinates, DECT radio module with free-field transmission range ~300 m, in buildings ~50 m

Annex 3

Hand-held reader BTR-2
Figure 77 - BTR-2

Figure 77 - BTR-2

- Manufacturer: MOBA Mobile Automation AG
- Operating temperature: -30 °C to 50 °C
- Enclosure Protection: IP65
- Enclosure: PC/ABS Bay blend (UL94)
- Dimensions: L: 140 x B: 63 x H: 31 mm
- Weight: 140 g
- Voltage range: Li Polymer rechargeable battery, 1000 mAh, permanently installed
- Antenna: internal
- Operating time: depends on application
- Data exchange: wireless communication, 50 m range
- Operator interface: One pushbutton, OLED status display and piezoelectric sounder
- Transponder reader: FDX/HDX LF-Transponder: TIRIS RO/RW HDX 134.2 kHz, FDX 125 kHz EM4100/EM4102, FDX 134 kHz EM4005/EM4105 and other compatible types
- Barcode scanner: Reads all 1D bar codes, including damaged and poorly printed codes

Annex 4. Comments from external reviewers

External Reviewer #1

13/09/2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	YES		3	The document uses a non-standard format for the title and sub title.
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	YES		3	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	YES		3	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	YES		3	The deliverable sections are not always clear because sometimes missing a bit more detailed descriptions
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?		NO		
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	YES		3	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		NO		
Are the indexes correct?		NO		
Is the written English correct?	YES		3	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		NO		
Glossary present in the document?		NO		

DARIO PELLEGRINO

ENG

External Reviewer #2

15/09/2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	yes		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	yes and no	yes and no		In the PAYT presented in the document, each user has their own containers, the user will pay for each container dumped (each dumped container e considered full). The PAYT in Cascais, the containers are for collective deposition and the user will pay for the number of uses of the container.
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	yes and no	yes and no		In the PAYT presented in the document, each user has their own containers, the user will pay for each container dumped (each dumped container e considered full). The PAYT in Cascais, the containers are for collective deposition and the user will pay for the number of uses of the container.
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	yes		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	yes		5	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	yes		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		no	1	
Are the indexes correct?	yes		5	
Is the written English correct?	yes		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	yes		5	
Glossary present in the document?		no	1	

Joao Dinis

EMAC

External Reviewer #3: ARS

12nd Sep, 2017

Issue	Score		Comments	
	Yes	No		
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		4	Missing a description of the interactions with other tasks and deliverables (e.g. D2.1)
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		4	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?		X	2	It seems that much of the document is a description of the already existing Mawis U2.0. The upgrades done to create Mawis U3.0, which is the objective of this deliverable according to the GA, are not easily understandable.
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	Technical description is ok but R&D is not very clear with respect to the existing module.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		X	2	Many figures are described but numbers are missing.
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		4	
Glossary present in the document?		X	1	Glossary is missing and it's needed given the many acronyms used.

Michele Giavini

ARS ambiente

External Reviewer #3: ARS

20th Nov, 2017

Issue	Score		Comments	
	Yes	No		
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		4	
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		4	Missing a description of the interactions with other tasks and deliverables (e.g. D2.1)
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		4	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		2	After the revision the upgrades done to create Mawis U3.0 are more understandable. Still a lot of description of the already existing Mawis U2.0.
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	Technical description is ok but R&D is not very clear with respect to the existing module.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		X	2	Many figures are numerated but caption text is missing..
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		4	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		4	
Glossary present in the document?	X		3	

Michele Giavini

ARS ambiente

**Subject: Horizon 2020 Framework Programme Grant Agreement: 688995
WASTE4THINK Review (Article 22 GA) PO Draft review report letter**

Abstract related to document D2.5

D2.5	Technical Documentation of R2: Collection Module	Major revision	<p>The deliverable offers a description of Moba existing system, deployed in container and vehicles for waste collection. The work is almost standalone, described as a product evolution of Moba offer. No interaction (Integration with Sotkon system (chamber provider in Cascais pilot) neither FIWARE integration) has started.</p> <p>Fig. 52 does not display its content properly. A number of references are missing throughout the document;</p> <p>D2.5 should be revised as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Correct English & editorial issues - Clarify the integration plan within the overall W4T architecture referring to D2.1 (interfaces, protocols, security, data model and security management) - Please include a section on the testing of the installed devices - Please provide information about the data security of the sensor layer. - Please provide a solution for the integration of the traffic data to optimise the collection route. - Please explain how filling level of bins will be monitored for the Zamudio pilot, since no filling sensors will be installed there, according to the review meeting.
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1. Comments from External Reviewers

1.1. External Reviewer #1: ENG

3st June, 2018

Issue	Ye s	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments	Comments MOBA
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5		
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		4		
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		4		
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		3	No clear descriptions in <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public information about container assignment and PAYT; MOBA internet platform (MIP) FIWARE platform integration 	The MIP description will be a case of D2.6 after the development is finished. The integration with FIWARE platform is described in chapters 4, 8.1 and 9.2.1 The implementation of PAYT module was planned for Cascais pilot. A real accounting rule is not possible there, because of law issues. An alternative incentive model is implemented in MAWISu2.0 as an intermediate solution. It shouldn't be template for other projects, because it is just a work around which is not supporting the real PAYT idea.
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		4		
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		3	No clear technical descriptions in <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MOBA internet platform (MIP) FIWARE platform integration 	The MIP is described in chapter 8.1 and 8.2. The comment from Jao says too technical, here it is not technical enough. It seems we found the right average.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5		
Are the indexes correct?	X		5		

Deliverable D2.5

Is the written English correct?	X	4
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X	4
Glossary present in the document?	X	4

Dario Pellegrino

dario.pellerino@eng.it

ENG

2. Comments from External Reviewers

1.2. External Reviewer #1: PARTNER

20th Nov, 2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?		X	3	Missing the billing module
Does the index of the document collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		4	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		4	
Does the content have sufficient technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	Document to technical. Difficulty analyzing.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		3	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		4	
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	

João Dinis